

Methodological report on the development of the *She Figures* Index

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September 2024

She Figures is the flagship report published by the European Commission (DG RTD) to monitor various aspects of gender equality in Research and Innovation (R&I) in EU Member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC). The initial focus of *She Figures* was on women's representation in science, from graduates to top leadership positions, including scientific boards. Over the years, there has been a gradual shift from an emphasis on women, and their individual journeys in scientific careers, towards gender¹ and an understanding of inequalities as structural and related to differences in power and privilege in R&I institutions and the sector more widely. This is reflected in the broader range of topics now covered by data in *She Figures* reports. Not only have the topics related to careers been broadened, for example looking at issues of mobility or precariousness, but there is also a wealth of information about the research content and the gender dimension within it.

The purpose of this methodological report is to present the development of this composite indicator, built upon a carefully selected set of robust indicators from the report. The *She Figures* Index provides a tool to measure the extent to which EU Member States have realised gender equality in the European Research Area (ERA). The key questions it seeks to answer, in a synthetic way, is: what is the state of gender equality in research and innovation in Europe? And, what progress has been made over time? The *She Figures* Index is related to two key policies areas. First, building upon the broad commitment of the European Commission outlined in the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-25, gender equality in R&I is address through European research funding, e.g. Horizon Europe, and through the new ERA Policy Agenda 2022-24, the Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe, which includes a dedicated action to promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness in R&I. Second, the New European Innovation Agenda, which seeks to promote the representation of women in innovation start-ups and scale-ups, and ensure that they close the gender funding gap.

This report first provides an overview of the development of the conceptual framework underpinning the *She Figures* Index, and the associated initial measurement framework. It then outlines the metrics developed, following by considerations on the available methodological space of alternative (weighting and aggregation). These are used to assess the correlation structure and refine the measurement framework, before conducting a multi-model analysis. The report concludes by presenting the final model and results from robustness checks.

1 Conceptual framework development

Gender inequalities in research and innovation can be understood in relation to five key dimensions: segregation in the pipeline; research careers and sectors; career progression; representation in decision-making positions; research participation; the gender dimension in research and innovation content (GDRIC).

¹ In line with the initial approach taken in *She Figures*, this work focuses on a binary understanding of gender, measured statistically through the categories of women and men. Nevertheless, it must be stressed that this is insufficient in that it disregards the experiences of those that identify outside of this binary classification, and that this prevents a full gender inclusion in research and innovation. It is hoped that using the category of women as a proxy for other gender minoritised groups will still deliver structural changes to the benefits of all.

1.1 Segregation in the pipeline

Women and men's representation in scientific careers remains unequal despite near parity in the number of graduates students, with women representing 48.1% of doctoral graduates in 2018 in the EU-27. Inequalities are exacerbated by segregation in disciplines, i.e. men are over-represented in STEM related subject areas (22.4% for Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and 29.4% for Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction in 2018 in the EU-27), and in sectors, i.e. gender differences between Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) or government and the private sector (in 2018 in the EU-27, women represented 42% of researchers in the higher education sector, 44% in the government sector and only 21% in the business enterprise sector).

1.2 Research careers and sectors

Gender differences are also apparent when it comes to family status and mobility (in 2019, on average in the EU-27, mobility for women and men was 22% during their PhD but with strong gender differences at national level, though men become more mobile than women in post-PhD stages with 24.9 for men and 19.8% for women). Gender differences in part-time employment (in 2019 in the EU-27, 11.1% of women researchers were employed part-time in the higher education sector, compared with 7.2% for men) and precarious contracts (in 2019 in the EU-27, 9% for women and 7.7% for men) has become more prominent, as well as that of differences in self-employment rather than careers (in 2018 in the EU-27, women represented 24.9% of self-employed Science and Engineering (S&E) and ICT professionals).

1.3 Career progression

Despite near parity between women and men at earlier stages of scientific careers, the R&I landscape is marked by profound inequalities as careers progress. Visually, this has been illustrated by the 'scissors' diagram displayed growing gender inequalities on the pathway from graduate student to Grade C, B and A positions² (in 2018, in the EU-27, the proportion of women decreased from 46.6% in Grade C positions, to 40.3% in Grade B positions, and only 26.2% in Grade A positions).

1.4 Representation in decision-making positions

The dearth of women's representation is even more pronounced in top leadership positions such as heads of institutions, boards or other scientific committees. In 2019 in the EU-27, women represented only 23.6% of heads of institutions in the higher education sector and 31.1% of the members of scientific and administrative boards, though only 24.5% of board leaders.

1.5 Research participation

Gender inequalities in representation infuse research content, what knowledge is produced and how it is applied. Women are under-represented as authors of scientific publications (in the period 2015-19 in the EU-27, the average proportion of women among authors on publications in all fields of R&D stood at 30%), and as inventors file a lower number of patents (in 2015-18, women contribution to patent

² Grades are defined as follows:

- A: The single highest grade at which research is normally conducted within the institutional or corporate system, e.g. a Full Professor
- B: All researchers working in positions that are not as senior as the top position but more senior than newly qualified PhD holders, e.g. Senior Lecturer, Associate Professor
- C: The first grade into which a newly qualified PhD graduate would normally be recruited within the institutional or corporate system, e.g. Lecture, Assistant Professor
- D: Either postgraduate students not yet holding a PhD degree who are engaged as researchers (on the payroll) or researchers working in posts that do not normally require a PhD

applications in the EU-27 was 6.2%³). Women are also both less likely to receive funding for their research, and when they do, it tends to be for smaller amounts (in 2019, women represented 38.0% and 34.9% of research funding applicants and beneficiaries, respectively).

1.6 Gender dimension in research and innovation content (GDRIC)

Finally, the gender dimension in publications and funded research projects continues to be largely absent and hardly considered (in 2015-19, in the EU-27, only 1.8% of publications included a gender dimension in their research and innovation content, only 1.65% and 0.2% respectively of Horizon 2020 projects integrated a gender dimension and an intersectionality approach).

1.7 Summary

These key themes are organised within five main dimensions to form a conceptual framework for the Index (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Conceptual framework for the *She Figures* Index

2 Measurement framework development

The conceptual framework was used as a basis for short-listing indicators from the 2021 edition of the *She Figures* report, the latest available indicators at the time of the development of the methodology. The criteria used for selection were that indicators not only needed to have conceptual relevance, but also needed to fulfil methodological criteria such as availability over time, and minimising missing values, following guidance from the European Commission's Joint Research Centre [*State-of-the-art report on current methodologies and practices for composite indicator development*](#).

The short-listing of indicators was done iteratively after extensive checks of missing values, correlation structures and Principal Components Analysis (PCA). PCA is a useful tool in that it can assess whether the selected indicators measure the same underlying construct. If that is the case, it is possible to verify that all indicators can be represented by a single component, using the Kaiser criterion of eigenvalues above 1 as a guide, ensuring that all rotated factors loadings are typically above 0.5, and that fit is adequate by checking that KMO values are normally above 0.5. These analyses are regarded as indicative only, as they are restricted to 27 observations for each indicator, i.e. one data point per

³ Contribution to patent applications is calculated as the sum of proportions for applications where there is woman alone, women-only teams, teams with at least 60% women and half the proportion where there is a mixed team, i.e. in the case of full gender equality, women's contribution across these categories should sum to 50%.

Member State. Results are presented for each dimension. In turn, this iterative process allowed for the conceptual framework to be translated into a rigorous measurement framework (see Section 5). In this section, we describe the process of selecting indicators for each of the dimensions identified in the conceptual framework.

2.1 Segregation in the pipeline

Indicators to measure horizontal segregation, i.e. the under- or over-representation of women and men in different subject areas, were selected in relation to doctoral graduates rather than researchers or grade level due to the large number of missing values for these indicators. The *She Figures* report provides a breakdown in ten subject areas⁴, and the correlations between women's representation in each of these subject areas was examined (Table 1).

Indicator selection is guided by conceptual relevance and coherence in the correlation structure, marked by positive correlation. Table 1 includes a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.39$) between the share of women in Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and in Engineering, manufacturing and construction. These areas also represent conceptually relevant subject areas to include in the *She Figures* Index given that there are typically subject areas where women are under-represented, despite the relevance of these domains for technological and digital growth in Europe. In 2018, in the EU-27, women represented 22.37% of doctoral graduates in ICTs, and 29.43% in Engineering, manufacturing and construction (She Figures, 2021). A further strong positive correlation exists between the share of women graduates in Arts and humanities and in Business and law ($r = 0.61$), although there is overall more of a gender balance in these domains where in 2018, in the EU-27, women represented 55.46% of doctoral graduates in Arts and humanities, and 44.76% in Business and law (She Figures, 2021). The share of women graduates in Arts and humanities is also positively correlated with the share of women in Engineering, manufacturing and construction ($r = 0.37$). Accordingly, all four indicators were short-listed.

⁴ Education; Arts and humanities; Social sciences, journalism and information; Business, administration and law; Natural sciences, mathematics and statistics; Information and Communication Technologies; Engineering, manufacturing and construction; Agriculture, forestry, fisheries and veterinary; Health and welfare; Services

Table 1 Correlation matrix – share of women as doctoral graduates by subject areas, 2018

Subject area:	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1 Education	1.00									
2 Arts and humanities	-0.42	1.00								
3 Social sciences, journalism and information	0.13	0.32	1.00							
4 Business, administration and law	-0.21	0.61	0.11	1.00						
5 Natural sciences, mathematics and statistics	0.34	-0.10	0.12	-0.07	1.00					
6 Information and Communication Technologies	-0.04	0.25	-0.01	0.08	0.05	1.00				
7 Engineering, manufacturing and construction	0.17	0.37	0.01	0.25	0.10	0.39	1.00			
8 Agriculture, forestry, fisheries and veterinary	-0.02	-0.08	-0.03	0.22	0.09	-0.08	-0.36	1.00		
9 Health and welfare	0.15	0.07	0.11	-0.18	0.17	-0.04	0.26	-0.32	1.00	
10 Services	0.19	-0.19	0.05	-0.57	-0.23	0.08	0.13	0.16	0.29	1.00

The results of the PCA in this dimension suggest that there are two underlying constructs (Table 2). An examination of the rotated solution for the two components solution shows that a differentiation between related subject areas, with ‘Arts and humanities’ and ‘Business and law’ combined into one component, and ‘ICTs’ and ‘Engineering, manufacturing, and construction’ in the other component (Table 3). This suggests that if all four indicators were to be retained in the *She Figures* Index, it may be necessary to account for this in the aggregation and structure, e.g. by through the creation of two sub-dimensions. To ensure that it is valid to aggregate all four indicators into a single construct, rotated factor loadings are produced for the one component solution (Table 4). These results suggest that a single dimension is possible, though with lower loadings for some indicators, and that it might therefore be more suitable to only retain some of the indicators. This is further examined in relation to the overall correlation structure (see Section 5).

Table 2 Principal Components – Eigen values and cumulative proportion of variance for segregation in the pipeline indicators

	Eigen value	Cumulative proportion of variance
Component 1	2.00	0.50
Component 2	1.06	0.76
Component 3	0.58	0.91
Component 4	0.36	1.00

Indicators: Share of women in Arts and humanities; Share of women in Business and law; Share of women in ICTs; Share of women in Engineering, manufacturing and construction

Table 3 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for segregation in the pipeline indicators (two components solution)

	Component 1	Component 2	KMO
Share of women in Arts and humanities	0.65		0.58
Share of women in Business and law	0.73		0.55
Share of women in ICTs		0.78	0.59
Share of women in Engineering, manufacturing and construction		0.61	0.69
Overall KMO			0.59

Values below |0.3| are blanked

Table 4 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for segregation in the pipeline indicators (one components solution)

	Component 1	KMO
Share of women in Arts and humanities	0.59	0.58
Share of women in Business and law	0.52	0.55
Share of women in ICTs	0.37	0.59
Share of women in Engineering, manufacturing and construction	0.49	0.69
Overall KMO		0.59

Values below |0.3| are blanked

2.2 Research careers and sectors

The results of the PCA in the dimension of research careers and sectors confirm that the three indicators correspond to a single underlying construct, accounting for 73% of the variation (Table 5) and with a good fit as indicated by a KMO value of 0.69 (Table 6). The rotated factors loadings are well above the threshold of 0.5, suggesting an appropriate structure.

Table 5 Principal Components – Eigen values and cumulative proportion of variance for research careers and sectors

	Eigen value	Cumulative proportion of variance
Component 1	2.19	0.73
Component 2	0.50	0.90
Component 3	0.31	1.00

Indicators: Share of women researchers in the higher education sector; Share of women researchers in the government sector; Share of women researchers in the business enterprise sector

Table 6 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for research careers and sectors

	Component 1	KMO
Share of women researchers in the higher education sector	0.60	0.64
Share of women researchers in the government sector	0.57	0.70
Share of women researchers in the business enterprise sector	0.55	0.75
Overall KMO		0.69

Values below |0.3| are blanked

2.3 Career progression

Indicators measuring gender representation in Grade A, Grade B and Grade C were considered for the dimension of career progression, that is all grades for which a doctoral qualification is expected. However, an in-depth assessment was performed to decide whether to use the set of all post-doctoral grades (A, B and C) or, alternatively, only Grades A and B. This assessment was motivated, methodologically, by the presence of missing values in the indicator measuring women's representation in Grade C positions, and importantly, conceptually, by whether the dimensions sought to measure career progression (Grades A and B represented the higher hierarchical levels in research organisations, i.e. typically representing Full or Associate Professors) or representation at different grades more generally.

The PCA analysis confirms that for the career progression dimension, the use of indicators measuring the share of women in Grade A and Grade B position represent a single underlying construct which account for 94% of the variance (Table 7). The rotated factors loading are both over the threshold of 0.5, and there is an adequate KMO value of 0.5 (Table 8).

Table 7 Principal Components – Eigen values and cumulative proportion of variance for career progression (Grades A and B)

	Eigen value	Cumulative proportion of variance
Component 1	1.88	0.94
Component 2	0.12	1.00

Indicators: Share of women among academic staff in Grade A positions; Share of women among academic staff in Grade B positions

Table 8 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for career progression (Grades A and B)

	Component 1	KMO
Share of women among academic staff in Grade A positions	0.71	0.50
Share of women among academic staff in Grade B positions	0.71	0.50
Overall KMO		0.50

Values below |0.3| are blanked

A PCA analysis was also carried out with the addition of the indicator measuring the share of women academic staff in Grade C positions, although conceptually, it was acknowledged that this would shift the interpretation of the dimension from career progression to representation. The results suggested that a one-dimension solution was most appropriate as the three indicators could be seen as representing a single underlying construct, accounting for 73% of the overall variance (Table 9). However, while the KMO was acceptable at 0.59, the rotated factors loading exceeded the thresholds of 0.5 only for the indicators measuring the share of women academic staff in Grades A and B (Table 10). This provided further evidence that retaining the indicator measuring the share of women academic staff in Grade C positions is not desirable.

Table 9 Principal Components – Eigen values and cumulative proportion of variance for career progression (Grades A, B and C)

	Eigen value	Cumulative proportion of variance
Component 1	2.18	0.73
Component 2	0.70	0.96
Component 3	0.12	1.00

Indicators: Share of women among academic staff in Grade A positions; Share of women among academic staff in Grade B positions; Share of women among academic staff in Grade C positions

Table 10 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for career progression (Grades A, B and C)

	Component 1	KMO
Share of women among academic staff in Grade A positions	0.62	0.56
Share of women among academic staff in Grade B positions	0.64	0.55
Share of women among academic staff in Grade C positions	0.45	0.84
Overall KMO		0.59

Values below |0.3| are blanked

2.4 Representation in decision-making positions

The PCA analysis confirmed that the indicators used to measure representation in decision-making positions represented a single underlying construct, accounting for 0.64 of variance (Table 11). The KMO suggested an adequate fit, with an overall value of 0.5 (Table 12). However, while indicators measuring the share of women as either leaders, or as members and leaders of boards demonstrated rotated factor loadings above 0.5, the indicator measuring the share of women among heads of institutions in the Higher Education Sector felt slightly short of that threshold. Nevertheless, given the importance of this indicator, it was considered further for inclusion and assessed further in the overall correlation structure (see Section 5).

Table 11 Principal Components – Eigen values and cumulative proportion of variance for representation in decision-making positions

	Eigen value	Cumulative proportion of variance
Component 1	1.91	0.64
Component 2	0.83	0.91
Component 3	0.26	1.00

Indicators: Share of women among heads of institutions in the Higher Education Sector (HES); Share of women on boards, as leaders; Share of women on boards, as members and leaders

Table 12 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for representation in decision-making positions

	Component 1	KMO
Share of women among heads of institutions in the Higher Education Sector (HES)	0.45	0.50
Share of women on boards, as leaders	0.67	0.50
Share of women on boards, as members and leaders	0.59	0.50
Overall KMO		0.50

Values below |0.3| are blanked

2.5 Research participation

The PCA analysis for the dimension of research participation confirmed that the three indicators examined represented a single underlying construct, with the first component explaining 71% of the variance (Table 13). All rotated factors loadings are above the threshold value of 0.5, with a KMO value of 0.66 suggesting a good fit (Table 14).

Table 13 Principal Components – Eigen values and cumulative proportion of variance for research participation

	Eigen value	Cumulative proportion of variance
Component 1	2.14	0.71
Component 2	0.57	0.90
Component 3	0.29	1.00

Indicators: Share of women among authors on publications in all fields of R&D; Distribution of patent applications by sex composition of the inventors' team; Share of women beneficiaries of research funding.

Table 14 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for research participation

	Component 1	KMO
Share of women among authors on publications in all fields of R&D	0.61	0.61
Distribution of patent applications by sex composition of the inventors' team	0.53	0.77
Share of women beneficiaries of research funding	0.58	0.65
Overall KMO		0.66

Values below |0.3| are blanked

2.6 The gender dimension in research and innovation content

Three indicators for the dimension of the gender dimension in research and innovation content (GDRIC) were examined in depth. The first indicator examines the share of publications at country level with a sex or gender dimension in their content. Two further indicators examined the extent to which Horizon 2020 projects includes a sex/gender dimension, and intersectional perspective, respectively.

The first PCA (Table 15) suggests that, as the second eigenvalue is marginally lower than the cut-off of 1, both a one- and a two-component solution should be examined. The one-component solution explains only 49% of the variance, though all three rotated factor loadings are above or near the threshold of 0.5 (Table 16). The two-component solution explains a greater proportion of the variance (82%), however the rotated factor loadings show a cross-loading, implying that this set of indicators is not able to accurately distinguish between two different sub-constructs (Table 17).

Looking at the indicators, it appears that the share of Horizon projects with a sex and gender perspective is both related to the percentage of a country's publications with a sex and gender dimension and with the proportion of Horizon projects with an intersectional perspective. This makes this solution unsuitable for inclusion in the *She Figures* Index. In addition, these solutions have a relatively low fit as indicated by a KMO value of 0.47.

Table 15 Principal Components – Eigen values and cumulative proportion of variance for the gender dimension in R&I content

	Eigen value	Cumulative proportion of variance
Component 1	1.47	0.49
Component 2	0.98	0.82
Component 3	0.55	1.00

Indicators: Percentage of a country's publications with a sex or gender dimension in their research content, by field of R&D; Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating a sex or gender dimension; Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating intersectionality

Table 16 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for the gender dimension in R&I content

	Component 1	KMO
Percentage of a country's publications with a sex or gender dimension in their research content, by field of R&D	0.48	0.46
Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating a sex or gender dimension	0.70	0.48
Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating intersectionality	0.53	0.47
Overall KMO		0.47

Values below |0.3| are blanked

Table 17 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for the gender dimension in R&I content

	Component 1	Component 2	KMO
Percentage of a country's publications with a sex or gender dimension in their research content, by field of R&D		0.88	0.46
Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating a sex or gender dimension	0.53	0.45	0.48
Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating intersectionality	0.84		0.47
Overall KMO			0.47

Values below |0.3| are blanked

Alternatives are to consider either the two indicators focusing on Horizon projects together, or the indicator focusing on publications on its own. Both solutions are feasible, as demonstrated by the PCA results below. Using the indicators focusing on Horizon projects measure a single construct that accounts for 67% of the variance (Table 18). The rotated factors loadings meet the threshold of 0.5, with adequate fit as demonstrated by a KMO value of 0.5 (Table 19). Different alternatives were further considered in the assessment of the correlation structure to determine the most appropriate indicators to select (see Section 5).

Table 18 Principal Components – Eigen values and cumulative proportion of variance for the gender dimension in R&I content

	Eigen value	Cumulative proportion of variance
Component 1	1.34	0.67
Component 2	0.66	1.00

Indicators: Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating a sex or gender dimension; Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating intersectionality

Table 19 Principal Components – Rotated factor loadings for the gender dimension in R&I content

	Component 1	KMO
Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating a sex or gender dimension	0.71	0.50
Percentage of country's Horizon projects integrating intersectionality	0.71	0.50
Overall KMO		0.50

Values below |0.3| are blanked

2.7 Summary

A final PCA analysis was performed with all short-listed indicators, however, did not yield results that could inform the structure of the *She Figures* Index and no clear solution was found. This is likely related to both the complexity of the multi-dimensional concept of gender equality in R&I, as well as the limited statistical power due the limited number of cases, i.e. 27 EU Member States. Nonetheless, the PCA analyses presented above inform a possible structure that can be examined iteratively through correlation analyses between the indicators, their dimensions, and the *She Figures* Index itself (see Section 5). The list of short-listed indicators in presented in Table 20. Before going further into the

assessment of the correlation structure of the *She Figures* Index, however, it is necessary to transpose these indicators into metrics, which is the topic discussed in the next section.

Table 20 Short-listed indicators (indicators examined further in italics)

Segregation in the pipeline	Research careers and sectors	Career progression	Representation in decision-making positions	Research participation	Gender dimension in Research and Innovation Content (GDRIC)
<i>Doctoral graduates Arts and Humanities</i>	Researchers in HES	Grade A	Heads of institutions	Authors	<i>Gender dimension in publications</i>
<i>Doctoral graduates Business and Law</i>	Researchers in Government	Grade B	Leaders of boards	Inventors	<i>Gender dimension in Horizon projects</i>
Doctoral graduates Information and Communication Technologies	Researchers in Business and Industry	<i>Grade C</i>	Leaders and members of boards	Beneficiaries of research funding	<i>Intersectional dimension in Horizon projects</i>
Doctoral graduates Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction					

3 Choice of metrics for shares/GDRIC

The short-listed indicators need to be transformed into metrics, i.e. a score ranging from 0 to 1, where 0 represents the lowest score and 1 the best score. There are two types of indicators, depending on the unit of analysis involved. The first type of indicators measures the share of women and men in respective aspects relevant to gender equality in R&I (unit of analysis: individuals), while the second type focuses on the share of publications or projects which include a sex or gender dimension (unit of analysis: projects or publications). This makes it necessary to consider carefully how to operationalise these into meaningful metrics, for later aggregation into a *She Figures* Index score.

3.1 Metrics for share indicators

For indicators focusing on the shares of women and men in different aspects of R&I, there two aspects to consider: (1) whether to adopt a metric that is linear or curvilinear; and (2) whether to cap at the parity point. In practice, this means that there are four types of metrics to consider, as illustrated below (Figure 1):

- Linear and capped: $X_W/0.5$ if $X_W \leq 0.5$, 1 otherwise
- Linear and uncapped: $\min(X_W, X_M)/0.5$
- Curvilinear and capped: $Blau(X_W, X_M)$ if $X_W \leq 0.5$, 1 otherwise
- Curvilinear and uncapped: $Blau(X_W, X_M)$

where X_W and X_M represent the share of women and men respectively for a given indicator, and where the Blau index is calculated as $Blau(X_W, X_M) = 2 \times (1 - (X_W^2 + X_M^2))$.

Figure 1 Metrics curvi/linear and un/capped

The following points should be considered in relation to how it is possible to interpret the different metrics presented above:

- Each metric measure gender equality in relation to exact parity, i.e. the maximum score of 1 is obtained where there are 50% of women and 50% of men.

- Linear metrics measure progress towards the goal of parity equally, regardless of whether women's share of representation is low or closer to parity, i.e. a score increase will be the same where women's share increases from 0% to 10% and when it increases from 40% to 50%.
- Curvilinear metrics, in contrast, reward progress at lower levels of representation more highly than when representation is near parity. In fact, where women's representation reaches 40%, the associated score is 0.96 when computed using a curvilinear metric. This may therefore be interpreted as sensitive to 'critical mass', that is where progress beyond 30% leads to smaller improvements in score, and with minimal progress in the score beyond 40% representation. Another benefit of using a curvilinear metric is that it puts less emphasis on the parity point (exactly 50% representation), and instead more apt at measuring 'gender balance' (on the interval 40%-60%).
- Capping is associated with a women's empowerment approach, i.e. reflecting policy priorities that focus on improving the situation of women.
- Uncapping is associated with a gender equality approach, i.e. reflecting policy priorities that seek to ensure that both women and men are equally represented.

After in-depth discussions about these different properties with Members of the Steering Group, consensus emerged on the use of a curvilinear uncapped metric. This is motivated by its ability to better take into account gender balance (i.e. a curvilinear metric provides high scores on the interval ranging from 40% to 60%) rather than focus narrowly on parity (i.e. highest score at the exact parity point, corresponding to 50%); as well as by its ability to consider not only situations where women are disadvantaged but also where this reverses towards men. Nevertheless, all four types of metrics were tested further as part of a multi-modelling process (see Section 6).

3.2 Metrics for levels indicators

For indicators focusing on levels, a different approach was needed. To create metrics ranging from 0 to 1, different variations of the min-max approach were considered. The min-max approach, in its basic form, rescales observations from 0 to 1. This means that it takes the observed minimum and maximum in the data as its interval boundaries. However, other interval boundaries can be considered, though this decision needs to be given a clear rationale. To help determine which interval boundaries to consider, a first step was to examine the distribution of all three indicators considered for the gender dimension. These indicators are characterised by very low values, ranging from 0% to just above 3%, out of a theoretical maximum of 100% (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Beeswarm plots of indicators for the gender dimension in research and innovation

Several options for metrics were examined. First taking the usual min-max approach, calculated on the basis of the observed minimum and maximum (MM); a min-max approach using the ceiling value of 10%, i.e. considering the range 0 to 10% (M10); and a min-max approach using the ceiling value of 100%, i.e. considering the full potential range of values from 0% to the theoretical maximum of 100% (M100). The range of respective scores for these three approaches are illustrated in Figure 3 for the indicator measuring the extent to which the gender dimension has been included in publications.

The first approach (MM) means that the scores can take on the full range of values between 0 and 1, and can be interpreted as the observed level of the extent to which the gender dimension has been used. The second (M10) and third (M100) approaches have more limited range of scores, and represent a more normative interpretation where the ceiling values used could be interpreted as targets or objectives. However, the arbitrary nature of these thresholds is problematic, in that it has yet to be determined what value to target, or even if a target is desirable or feasible. Despite these notes of caution, all three options were included in the multi-modelling assessment.

Figure 3 Beeswarm plots of metrics for the gender dimension in publications by method (MM, M10, M100)

3.3 Summary

This section has presented the different metrics considered for building the *She Figures* Index, differentiating the approaches needed where the unit of analysis is the share of women and men, or the level of integration of a gender dimension in research and innovation content. The next step was to examine how to combine metrics within the measurement framework, and to consider further choices in relation to aggregation and weighting. This methodological space of alternatives is discussed next.

4 Methodological space of alternatives (aggregation, weights)

The two main aspects characterising the methodological space of alternatives are aggregation and weights. In this section, the different alternatives considered, and their properties are outlined.

4.1 Aggregation

Several different methods for aggregating the indicators within domains and sub-domains exist. The difference in these methods lie in the level of compensation they allow between indicators, sub-dimensions or dimensions. A summary table outlines these different levels of compensation, together with some illustrations (Table 21). The table provides three examples, each with three indicators.

In example 1, all three indicators are equal, with a value of 50, representing a situation where there is full equality. In example 2, there is moderate inequality, as the three indicators range from 40 to 60, though the average is the same as example 1. In example 3, there is greater inequality, as despite maintaining an average of 50, the range increases from 10 to 90. Using an arithmetic mean allows for full compensation between indicators, and does not distinguish between the disparities in indicators within the three examples. Using a geometric mean introduces a ‘penalty, providing a mean of 50 when indicators are equal but increasingly pulling down this score as inequality between indicators increases. This penalisation is even more blatant when a harmonic mean is used. It is important to note that it is not necessary to apply the same aggregation methods at all levels (indicators, sub-domains, domains), and indeed, allowing for full compensation at levels closer to the indicators themselves might be appropriate.

Overall, aggregation methods therefore vary in their approach to compensation between indicators, sub-dimensions and dimensions. The arithmetic mean provides full compensation across indicators, while the geometric and harmonic means increasingly penalise situations where there are inequalities between indicators. The choice of indicators was discussed with SG members, who expressed a preference for simpler methods, i.e. arithmetic mean, if this resulted in similar scores, compared with other methods. This was further assessment as part of the multi-modelling approach (see Section 6).

Table 21 Summary table of aggregation methods and associated compensations

Indicator 1	Indicator 2	Indicator 3	Arithmetic	Geometric	Harmonic
			$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$	$\left(\prod_{i=1}^n x_i\right)^{1/n}$	$\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{-1}}{n}\right)^{-1}$
			Full compensation	Medium compensation	Limited compensation
Example 1	50	50	50	50	50
Example 2	40	50	60	49.3	48.6
Example 3	10	50	90	35.6	22.9

4.2 Weighting

Another consideration is the weighting scheme adopted to compute the scores of the Index. The four options examined in the construction of the *She Figures* Index were as follows:

- The simplest choice that can be adopted is to simply apply equal weights to all indicators and sub-pillar. This is a choice that is easily communicable and interpretable, but which despite how it appears is not a neutral one. This is because the correlation structure of the indicators means that some indicators have greater influence on the overall results of the Index than others.
- Indicators that have larger variability can have more bearing on the final scores. Equalising standard deviations across indicators accounts for this, and equalises standard deviations across indicators by calculating the change by 1% standard deviation increase and rescaling to add up to 1.
- Where it is possible to conduct a principal component analysis, the factors loadings and the proportion of total variance explained by each factor can be used to derive weights at indicator and pillar level.
- Another approach is to consult with relevant stakeholders and derive a set of weights that is informed by the importance given to each pillar by the community of practice. Generally, it is not possible to apply budget allocation at the level of indicators because of the level of details that is involved. This is another easily communicable and interpretable method, however it is highly subjective and dependent on the representativeness of the community from which these weights are derived.

After discussion with the SG members, it was decided to only retain the options of using equal weights or budget allocation weights. This is because, due to the lack of statistical power linked to only working with data from 27 Member States, it was not possible to derive meaningful PCA-based weights (see Section 2); and because equalising standard deviations across indicators means losing information about the actual variability of the indicators across the different countries, seen as valuable information in its own right.

A budget allocation exercise was carried out. This exercise provided a template with all six dimensions, asking respondents to allocate weights to each and to provide a short rationale to explain their weight allocation. Where necessary, weights were rescaled to ensure they summed to 1. Five submissions were returned (Table 22), three of which expressing a preference for equal weights (W1). A second suggestion (W2) allocated more weight to the dimensions of progression and decision-making, on the basis that career advancement and participation play a key role in gender equality and are more in the limelight of politicians and the general public. The third suggestion (W3) allocated more weights to the gender dimension, arguing that it is an emerging issue in research and innovation that much be pushed more than the other dimensions.

Table 22 Summary of weight budget allocation

	W1	W2	W3
Segregation in the pipeline	1/6	1/8	1/8
Research careers and sectors	1/6	1/8	1/8
Career progression	1/6	1/4	1/8
Representation in decision-making positions	1/6	1/4	1/8
Research participation	1/6	1/8	1/8
The gender dimension in research and innovation content	1/6	1/8	3/8

4.3 Summary

The different options considered for aggregation and weighting were presented above. In the next section, the assessment of the correlation structure is discussed, bringing together these results with that of the initial development of the measurement framework and the various metric options.

5 Assessment of the correlation structure and refinement of the measurement framework

To refine the measurement framework, initial tests were performed using a limited choice of methods for an initial assessment of the correlation structure. These tests were performed using a symmetric linear metric for shares indicators, equal weights and the arithmetic mean. The use of different weights and aggregation method does not significantly modify the correlation structure, as the relative positions of scores at different levels are normally preserved. The same applies to metrics that rely on a linear or curvilinear approach. However, the use of an uncapped metric can produce slightly different results, as by construction, different values are obtained when women exceed the parity point. However, it was clear from the SG that there was a strong preference for an uncapped metric approach, and it was therefore used for the initial assessment (and later test in the multi-modelling assessment, see Section 6). Different options for metric to measure the level of gender dimension in research and innovation were tested, as one of the aim of the initial assessment was to understand which metric might be more suitable methodologically.

The assessment of the correlation structure is an iterative process, examining different solutions and seeking refinements to the measurement framework. The procedure used is an adaptation of the audit methodology developed by JRC COIN (for more information, see [About the Competence Centre on Composite Indicators and Scoreboards | Knowledge for policy \(europa.eu\)](#)), and relies on the following checks:

- Examining the correlations between indicators with the same dimension with ideally moderate to strong positive correlations coefficients (i.e. typically 0.5 to 0.8). This confirms that these indicators represent a single underlying construct, building upon the PCA analysis (see Section 2).
- Ensuring that there are no strong negative correlations (i.e. below -0.4) between indicators in a given dimension, and indicators in another dimension. This ensures that there are no trade-off between dimensions, which would hinder the interpretability of the scores of the Index.
- Examining the correlations between indicators and the scores for their respective dimensions, to ensure that they are sufficiently contributing (i.e. above 0.5, and ideally no less than 0.4).
- Examining the correlations between indicators, dimensions and Index scores, to ensure that they contribute substantially to the final Index score (i.e. above 0.5, and ideally no less than 0.4).
- Screen for very high correlations (i.e. 0.9 and above) among indicators, which may signal that two indicators are so strongly correlated that do in fact represent only a single underlying construct.

5.1 Testing the gender dimension metrics

Three initial tests were conducted using all 19 short-listed, using the M100, M10 and MM metric in turn for indicators measuring the gender dimension in research and innovation content (Table 23, Table 25 and Table 24, respectively). This revealed several potential issues:

1. A moderate negative correlation between the share of women and men as doctoral graduates in Arts and Humanities and the share of women and men in Grades A and B positions.
2. Low contribution of the indicator measuring the share of women and men in Grade C positions to the score of the career progression dimension
3. Marginal contribution of the indicator measuring the shares of women and men as doctoral graduates in Business and Law and as Member and Leaders of boards to the Index score.
4. No contribution of the two indicators measuring the extent to which the sex and gender dimension has been included in publication and Horizon projects; and the indicator measuring the share of women and men in Arts and Humanities to the Index score.
5. No contribution of the gender dimension in research and innovation content to the Index score in the case where M100 and M10 is used, though there is a contribution when the MM method is used.

Consequently, this suggested that the most suitable method for the metrics capturing the gender dimension in research and innovation content is the MM method.

Table 23 Test 1 - All shares indicators (16) and gender dimension levels indicators (3) using M100 method

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
1 Doctoral Graduates - Arts and Humanities	1.00																									
2 Doctoral Graduates - Business and law	0.38	1.00																								
3 Doctoral Graduates - ICTs	0.15	0.37	1.00																							
4 Doctoral Graduates - Engineering manufacturing and construction	0.40	0.54	0.39	1.00																						
5 Researchers - Higher Education	0.10	0.25	0.54	0.54	1.00																					
6 Researchers - Government	0.44	0.50	0.36	0.63	0.52	1.00																				
7 Researchers - Business Enterprise	-0.20	-0.17	0.44	0.26	0.49	0.21	1.00																			
8 Grade A	-0.43	-0.19	0.24	0.11	0.49	0.03	0.56	1.00																		
9 Grade B	-0.48	-0.09	0.14	0.18	0.49	0.06	0.43	0.74	1.00																	
10 Grade C	0.47	0.52	0.33	0.72	0.48	0.67	-0.10	-0.12	-0.03	1.00																
11 Heads of institutions	0.05	-0.09	0.20	0.15	0.25	0.13	0.31	0.36	0.29	-0.03	1.00															
12 Leaders	-0.13	0.22	0.23	0.08	0.30	0.37	0.21	0.13	0.25	0.03	0.40	1.00														
13 Members and Leaders	-0.35	-0.02	0.18	-0.20	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.24	-0.01	0.25	0.66	1.00													
14 Authors	-0.13	0.09	0.44	0.51	0.78	0.45	0.68	0.71	0.64	0.38	0.31	0.18	0.03	1.00												
15 Patents	-0.05	0.06	0.27	0.51	0.59	0.20	0.48	0.41	0.55	0.16	0.14	0.02	-0.23	0.56	1.00											
16 Beneficiaries of funding	0.08	0.29	0.54	0.54	0.70	0.45	0.51	0.38	0.36	0.32	0.45	0.47	0.24	0.64	0.49	1.00										
17 Publications with a sex or gender dimension M100	0.00	-0.30	-0.31	-0.14	0.09	-0.08	0.02	0.08	0.35	-0.25	0.25	0.26	0.05	-0.07	0.08	-0.03	1.00									
18 Horizon projects with a sex or gender dimension M100	-0.08	-0.36	-0.23	-0.03	-0.09	-0.28	-0.22	0.08	0.21	0.05	0.07	-0.12	0.13	0.03	-0.20	-0.27	0.31	1.00								
19 Horizon projects with an intersectional dimension M100	0.17	0.29	0.46	0.25	0.22	0.19	-0.08	-0.19	-0.04	0.41	0.27	0.41	0.54	0.11	-0.17	0.23	0.02	0.34	1.00							
20 Segregation in the pipeline	0.55	0.82	0.70	0.80	0.52	0.66	0.15	-0.03	-0.01	0.69	0.10	0.19	-0.08	0.36	0.30	0.54	-0.29	-0.27	0.42	1.00						
21 Research careers and sectors	0.11	0.20	0.57	0.58	0.81	0.71	0.80	0.47	0.41	0.38	0.30	0.37	0.04	0.82	0.54	0.69	0.01	-0.27	0.11	0.53	1.00					
22 Career progression	-0.28	0.05	0.33	0.43	0.69	0.31	0.47	0.85	0.86	0.32	0.32	0.20	0.14	0.84	0.54	0.51	0.11	0.16	0.04	0.25	0.61	1.00				
23 Representation in decision-making positions	-0.18	0.09	0.26	0.03	0.26	0.26	0.23	0.21	0.31	0.01	0.64	0.92	0.80	0.21	-0.02	0.49	0.24	0.00	0.51	0.11	0.32	0.26	1.00			
24 Research participation	0.00	0.22	0.53	0.61	0.81	0.47	0.64	0.55	0.55	0.35	0.41	0.35	0.11	0.84	0.70	0.93	-0.02	-0.20	0.14	0.51	0.81	0.71	0.37	1.00		
25 Gender dimension in research and innovation content	-0.03	-0.37	-0.27	-0.07	0.03	-0.19	-0.13	0.08	0.33	-0.07	0.22	0.13	0.16	-0.01	-0.09	-0.15	0.79	0.82	0.32	-0.29	-0.15	0.16	0.20	-0.12	1.00	
26 Index	0.04	0.39	0.63	0.60	0.77	0.62	0.55	0.49	0.54	0.43	0.54	0.66	0.39	0.74	0.46	0.84	0.05	-0.14	0.42	0.62	0.82	0.70	0.68	0.86	-0.01	1.00

Table 24 Test 2 - All shares indicators (16) and gender dimension levels indicators (3) using M10 method

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
1 Doctoral Graduates - Arts and Humanities	1.00																									
2 Doctoral Graduates - Business and law	0.38	1.00																								
3 Doctoral Graduates - ICTs	0.15	0.37	1.00																							
4 Doctoral Graduates - Engineering manufacturing and construction	0.40	0.54	0.39	1.00																						
5 Researchers - Higher Education	0.10	0.25	0.54	0.54	1.00																					
6 Researchers - Government	0.44	0.50	0.36	0.63	0.52	1.00																				
7 Researchers - Business Enterprise	-0.20	-0.17	0.44	0.26	0.49	0.21	1.00																			
8 Grade A	-0.43	-0.19	0.24	0.11	0.49	0.03	0.56	1.00																		
9 Grade B	-0.48	-0.09	0.14	0.18	0.49	0.06	0.43	0.74	1.00																	
10 Grade C	0.47	0.52	0.33	0.72	0.48	0.67	-0.10	-0.12	-0.03	1.00																
11 Heads of institutions	0.05	-0.09	0.20	0.15	0.25	0.13	0.31	0.36	0.29	-0.03	1.00															
12 Leaders	-0.13	0.22	0.23	0.08	0.30	0.37	0.21	0.13	0.25	0.03	0.40	1.00														
13 Members and Leaders	-0.35	-0.02	0.18	-0.20	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.24	-0.01	0.25	0.66	1.00													
14 Authors	-0.13	0.09	0.44	0.51	0.78	0.45	0.68	0.71	0.64	0.38	0.31	0.18	0.03	1.00												
15 Patents	-0.05	0.06	0.27	0.51	0.59	0.20	0.48	0.41	0.55	0.16	0.14	0.02	-0.23	0.56	1.00											
16 Beneficiaries of funding	0.08	0.29	0.54	0.54	0.70	0.45	0.51	0.38	0.36	0.32	0.45	0.47	0.24	0.64	0.49	1.00										
17 Publications with a sex or gender dimension MM	0.00	-0.30	-0.31	-0.14	0.09	-0.08	0.02	0.08	0.35	-0.25	0.25	0.26	0.05	-0.07	0.08	-0.03	1.00									
18 Horizon projects with a sex or gender dimension MM	-0.08	-0.36	-0.23	-0.03	-0.09	-0.28	-0.22	0.08	0.21	0.05	0.07	-0.12	0.13	0.03	-0.20	-0.27	0.31	1.00								
19 Horizon projects with an intersectional dimension MM	0.17	0.29	0.46	0.25	0.22	0.19	-0.08	-0.19	-0.04	0.41	0.27	0.41	0.54	0.11	-0.17	0.23	0.02	0.34	1.00							
20 Segregation in the pipeline	0.55	0.82	0.70	0.80	0.52	0.66	0.15	-0.03	-0.01	0.69	0.10	0.19	-0.08	0.36	0.30	0.54	-0.29	-0.27	0.42	1.00						
21 Research careers and sectors	0.11	0.20	0.57	0.58	0.81	0.71	0.80	0.47	0.41	0.38	0.30	0.37	0.04	0.82	0.54	0.69	0.01	-0.27	0.11	0.53	1.00					
22 Career progression	-0.28	0.05	0.33	0.43	0.69	0.31	0.47	0.85	0.86	0.32	0.32	0.20	0.14	0.84	0.54	0.51	0.11	0.16	0.04	0.25	0.61	1.00				
23 Representation in decision-making positions	-0.18	0.09	0.26	0.03	0.26	0.26	0.23	0.21	0.31	0.01	0.64	0.92	0.80	0.21	-0.02	0.49	0.24	0.00	0.51	0.11	0.32	0.26	1.00			
24 Research participation	0.00	0.22	0.53	0.61	0.81	0.47	0.64	0.55	0.55	0.35	0.41	0.35	0.11	0.84	0.70	0.93	-0.02	-0.20	0.14	0.51	0.81	0.71	0.37	1.00		
25 Gender dimension in research and innovation content	-0.03	-0.37	-0.28	-0.08	0.03	-0.19	-0.12	0.08	0.34	-0.09	0.22	0.13	0.16	-0.01	-0.08	-0.15	0.81	0.81	0.31	-0.30	-0.14	0.16	0.20	-0.11	1.00	
26 Index	0.04	0.36	0.61	0.60	0.77	0.61	0.54	0.50	0.56	0.43	0.55	0.67	0.40	0.74	0.46	0.83	0.10	-0.08	0.44	0.60	0.81	0.71	0.69	0.85	0.05	1.00

Table 25 Test 3 - All shares indicators (16) and gender dimension levels indicators (3) using MM method

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
1 Doctoral Graduates - Arts and Humanities	1.00																									
2 Doctoral Graduates - Business and law	0.38	1.00																								
3 Doctoral Graduates - ICTs	0.15	0.37	1.00																							
4 Doctoral Graduates - Engineering manufacturing and construction	0.40	0.54	0.39	1.00																						
5 Researchers - Higher Education	0.10	0.25	0.54	0.54	1.00																					
6 Researchers - Government	0.44	0.50	0.36	0.63	0.52	1.00																				
7 Researchers - Business Enterprise	-0.20	-0.17	0.44	0.26	0.49	0.21	1.00																			
8 Grade A	-0.43	-0.19	0.24	0.11	0.49	0.03	0.56	1.00																		
9 Grade B	-0.48	-0.09	0.14	0.18	0.49	0.06	0.43	0.74	1.00																	
10 Grade C	0.47	0.52	0.33	0.72	0.48	0.67	-0.10	-0.12	-0.03	1.00																
11 Heads of institutions	0.05	-0.09	0.20	0.15	0.25	0.13	0.31	0.36	0.29	-0.03	1.00															
12 Leaders	-0.13	0.22	0.23	0.08	0.30	0.37	0.21	0.13	0.25	0.03	0.40	1.00														
13 Members and Leaders	-0.35	-0.02	0.18	-0.20	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.24	-0.01	0.25	0.66	1.00													
14 Authors	-0.13	0.09	0.44	0.51	0.78	0.45	0.68	0.71	0.64	0.38	0.31	0.18	0.03	1.00												
15 Patents	-0.05	0.06	0.27	0.51	0.59	0.20	0.48	0.41	0.55	0.16	0.14	0.02	-0.23	0.56	1.00											
16 Beneficiaries of funding	0.08	0.29	0.54	0.54	0.70	0.45	0.51	0.38	0.36	0.32	0.45	0.47	0.24	0.64	0.49	1.00										
17 Publications with a sex or gender dimension MM	0.00	-0.30	-0.31	-0.14	0.09	-0.08	0.02	0.08	0.35	-0.25	0.25	0.26	0.05	-0.07	0.08	-0.03	1.00									
18 Horizon projects with a sex or gender dimension MM	-0.08	-0.36	-0.23	-0.03	-0.09	-0.28	-0.22	0.08	0.21	0.05	0.07	-0.12	0.13	0.03	-0.20	-0.27	0.31	1.00								
19 Horizon projects with an intersectional dimension MM	0.17	0.29	0.46	0.25	0.22	0.19	-0.08	-0.19	-0.04	0.41	0.27	0.41	0.54	0.11	-0.17	0.23	0.02	0.34	1.00							
20 Segregation in the pipeline	0.55	0.82	0.70	0.80	0.52	0.66	0.15	-0.03	-0.01	0.69	0.10	0.19	-0.08	0.36	0.30	0.54	-0.29	-0.27	0.42	1.00						
21 Research careers and sectors	0.11	0.20	0.57	0.58	0.81	0.71	0.80	0.47	0.41	0.38	0.30	0.37	0.04	0.82	0.54	0.69	0.01	-0.27	0.11	0.53	1.00					
22 Career progression	-0.28	0.05	0.33	0.43	0.69	0.31	0.47	0.85	0.86	0.32	0.32	0.20	0.14	0.84	0.54	0.51	0.11	0.16	0.04	0.25	0.61	1.00				
23 Representation in decision-making positions	-0.18	0.09	0.26	0.03	0.26	0.26	0.23	0.21	0.31	0.01	0.64	0.92	0.80	0.21	-0.02	0.49	0.24	0.00	0.51	0.11	0.32	0.26	1.00			
24 Research participation	0.00	0.22	0.53	0.61	0.81	0.47	0.64	0.55	0.55	0.35	0.41	0.35	0.11	0.84	0.70	0.93	-0.02	-0.20	0.14	0.51	0.81	0.71	0.37	1.00		
25 Gender dimension in research and innovation content	0.07	-0.11	0.04	0.07	0.14	-0.03	-0.12	-0.04	0.23	0.14	0.30	0.32	0.39	0.04	-0.14	0.02	0.61	0.73	0.73	0.01	-0.03	0.14	0.42	0.00	1.00	
26 Index	0.06	0.30	0.56	0.55	0.72	0.54	0.44	0.42	0.54	0.43	0.57	0.69	0.48	0.66	0.36	0.74	0.24	0.12	0.61	0.55	0.70	0.65	0.74	0.75	0.52	1.00

5.2 Testing shares indicators on segregation, career progression and the gender and intersectional dimensions

The next iteration tested the correlation structure after removing indicators measuring the share of women and men as doctoral students in Arts and Humanities, as well as in Business and Law (Table 26). Both indicators are related to the same underlying construct (see PCA analysis, Section 2.1), with no or low contributions to the Index score. Further, the removal of these indicators serves to remove the problems of the negative correlations with other indicators identified in Table 23, Table 25 and Table 24.

This is followed by another iteration where the indicator measuring the share of women and men in Grade C positions is removed (Table 27). This is related to the low contribution of this indicator to the score of its associated dimension, as well as conceptual and measurement issues examined in the PCA analysis (see Section 2.3). The results confirmed that, empirically, there is a stronger correlation structure after this indicator is omitted.

The final iteration consists of removing indicators related to the gender and intersectional dimensions in Horizon projects (Table 28). This is motivated by considering the wider scope of the indicator based on publications, rather than Horizon projects given that these only represent a small proportion of research and innovation content in Europe. This provides a suitable correlation structure, with indicators contributing to all dimensions, and with one exception to the Index scores. The exception is that of the share of women and men as members and leaders of boards, however, it nevertheless represents a marginal contribution and is an important indicator to retain conceptually.

Table 26 Test 4 – After removing the share of women and men as graduates in Arts & Humanities and Business & Law

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
1 Doctoral Graduates - ICTs	1.00																							
2 Doctoral Graduates - Engineering manufacturing and construction	0.39	1.00																						
3 Researchers - Higher Education	0.54	0.54	1.00																					
4 Researchers - Government	0.36	0.63	0.52	1.00																				
5 Researchers - Business Enterprise	0.44	0.26	0.49	0.21	1.00																			
6 Grade A	0.24	0.11	0.49	0.03	0.56	1.00																		
7 Grade B	0.14	0.18	0.49	0.06	0.43	0.74	1.00																	
8 Grade C	0.33	0.72	0.48	0.67	-0.10	-0.12	-0.03	1.00																
9 Heads of institutions	0.20	0.15	0.25	0.13	0.31	0.36	0.29	-0.03	1.00															
10 Leaders	0.23	0.08	0.30	0.37	0.21	0.13	0.25	0.03	0.40	1.00														
11 Members and Leaders	0.18	-0.20	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.24	-0.01	0.25	0.66	1.00													
12 Authors	0.44	0.51	0.78	0.45	0.68	0.71	0.64	0.38	0.31	0.18	0.03	1.00												
13 Patents	0.27	0.51	0.59	0.20	0.48	0.41	0.55	0.16	0.14	0.02	-0.23	0.56	1.00											
14 Beneficiaries of funding	0.54	0.54	0.70	0.45	0.51	0.38	0.36	0.32	0.45	0.47	0.24	0.64	0.49	1.00										
15 Publications with a sex or gender dimension MM	-0.31	-0.14	0.09	-0.08	0.02	0.08	0.35	-0.25	0.25	0.26	0.05	-0.07	0.08	-0.03	1.00									
16 Horizon projects with a sex or gender dimension MM	-0.23	-0.03	-0.09	-0.28	-0.22	0.08	0.21	0.05	0.07	-0.12	0.13	0.03	-0.20	-0.27	0.31	1.00								
17 Horizon projects with an intersectional dimension MM	0.46	0.25	0.22	0.19	-0.08	-0.19	-0.04	0.41	0.27	0.41	0.54	0.11	-0.17	0.23	0.02	0.34	1.00							
18 Segregation in the pipeline	0.85	0.82	0.65	0.59	0.42	0.21	0.19	0.62	0.21	0.19	0.00	0.56	0.46	0.65	-0.27	-0.16	0.43	1.00						
19 Research careers and sectors	0.57	0.58	0.81	0.71	0.80	0.47	0.41	0.38	0.30	0.37	0.04	0.82	0.54	0.69	0.01	-0.27	0.11	0.69	1.00					
20 Career progression	0.33	0.43	0.69	0.31	0.47	0.85	0.86	0.32	0.32	0.20	0.14	0.84	0.54	0.51	0.11	0.16	0.04	0.46	0.61	1.00				
21 Representation in decision-making positions	0.26	0.03	0.26	0.26	0.23	0.21	0.31	0.01	0.64	0.92	0.80	0.21	-0.02	0.49	0.24	0.00	0.51	0.18	0.32	0.26	1.00			
22 Research participation	0.53	0.61	0.81	0.47	0.64	0.55	0.55	0.35	0.41	0.35	0.11	0.84	0.70	0.93	-0.02	-0.20	0.14	0.68	0.81	0.71	0.37	1.00		
23 Gender dimension in research and innovation content	0.04	0.07	0.14	-0.03	-0.12	-0.04	0.23	0.14	0.30	0.32	0.39	0.04	-0.14	0.02	0.61	0.73	0.73	0.06	-0.03	0.14	0.42	0.00	1.00	
24 Index	0.60	0.56	0.73	0.51	0.50	0.46	0.57	0.41	0.57	0.65	0.46	0.69	0.40	0.75	0.22	0.13	0.59	0.70	0.73	0.68	0.71	0.77	0.50	1.00

Table 27 Test 5 – After removing the share of women and men as in Grade C positions

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	
1 Doctoral Graduates - ICTs	1.00																							
2 Doctoral Graduates - Engineering manufacturing and construction	0.39	1.00																						
3 Researchers - Higher Education	0.54	0.54	1.00																					
4 Researchers - Government	0.36	0.63	0.52	1.00																				
5 Researchers - Business Enterprise	0.44	0.26	0.49	0.21	1.00																			
6 Grade A	0.24	0.11	0.49	0.03	0.56	1.00																		
7 Grade B	0.14	0.18	0.49	0.06	0.43	0.74	1.00																	
8 Heads of institutions	0.20	0.15	0.25	0.13	0.31	0.36	0.29	1.00																
9 Leaders	0.23	0.08	0.30	0.37	0.21	0.13	0.25	0.40	1.00															
10 Members and Leaders	0.18	-0.20	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.24	0.25	0.66	1.00														
11 Authors	0.44	0.51	0.78	0.45	0.68	0.71	0.64	0.31	0.18	0.03	1.00													
12 Patents	0.27	0.51	0.59	0.20	0.48	0.41	0.55	0.14	0.02	-0.23	0.56	1.00												
13 Beneficiaries of funding	0.54	0.54	0.70	0.45	0.51	0.38	0.36	0.45	0.47	0.24	0.64	0.49	1.00											
14 Publications with a sex or gender dimension MM	-0.31	-0.14	0.09	-0.08	0.02	0.08	0.35	0.25	0.26	0.05	-0.07	0.08	-0.03	1.00										
15 Horizon projects with a sex or gender dimension MM	-0.23	-0.03	-0.09	-0.28	-0.22	0.08	0.21	0.07	-0.12	0.13	0.03	-0.20	-0.27	0.31	1.00									
16 Horizon projects with an intersectional dimension MM	0.46	0.25	0.22	0.19	-0.08	-0.19	-0.04	0.27	0.41	0.54	0.11	-0.17	0.23	0.02	0.34	1.00								
17 Segregation in the pipeline	0.85	0.82	0.65	0.59	0.42	0.21	0.19	0.21	0.19	0.00	0.56	0.46	0.65	-0.27	-0.16	0.43	1.00							
18 Research careers and sectors	0.57	0.58	0.81	0.71	0.80	0.47	0.41	0.30	0.37	0.04	0.82	0.54	0.69	0.01	-0.27	0.11	0.69	1.00						
19 Career progression	0.21	0.15	0.52	0.04	0.53	0.95	0.91	0.35	0.19	0.15	0.72	0.51	0.40	0.21	0.15	-0.13	0.22	0.48	1.00					
20 Representation in decision-making positions	0.26	0.03	0.26	0.26	0.23	0.21	0.31	0.64	0.92	0.80	0.21	-0.02	0.49	0.24	0.00	0.51	0.18	0.32	0.27	1.00				
21 Research participation	0.53	0.61	0.81	0.47	0.64	0.55	0.55	0.41	0.35	0.11	0.84	0.70	0.93	-0.02	-0.20	0.14	0.68	0.81	0.59	0.37	1.00			
22 Gender dimension in research and innovation content	0.04	0.07	0.14	-0.03	-0.12	-0.04	0.23	0.30	0.32	0.39	0.04	-0.14	0.02	0.61	0.73	0.73	0.06	-0.03	0.08	0.42	0.00	1.00		
23 Index	0.58	0.51	0.73	0.46	0.54	0.54	0.63	0.59	0.65	0.46	0.71	0.42	0.74	0.25	0.14	0.54	0.66	0.72	0.62	0.71	0.78	0.49	1.00	

Table 28 Test 6 – After removing the indicators on the gender and intersectional dimensions in Horizon projects

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1 Doctoral Graduates - ICTs	1.00																				
2 Doctoral Graduates - Engineering manufacturing and construction	0.39	1.00																			
3 Researchers - Higher Education	0.54	0.54	1.00																		
4 Researchers - Government	0.36	0.63	0.52	1.00																	
5 Researchers - Business Enterprise	0.44	0.26	0.49	0.21	1.00																
6 Grade A	0.24	0.11	0.49	0.03	0.56	1.00															
7 Grade B	0.14	0.18	0.49	0.06	0.43	0.74	1.00														
8 Heads of institutions	0.20	0.15	0.25	0.13	0.31	0.36	0.29	1.00													
9 Leaders	0.23	0.08	0.30	0.37	0.21	0.13	0.25	0.40	1.00												
10 Members and Leaders	0.18	-0.20	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.24	0.25	0.66	1.00											
11 Authors	0.44	0.51	0.78	0.45	0.68	0.71	0.64	0.31	0.18	0.03	1.00										
12 Patents	0.27	0.51	0.59	0.20	0.48	0.41	0.55	0.14	0.02	-0.23	0.56	1.00									
13 Beneficiaries of funding	0.54	0.54	0.70	0.45	0.51	0.38	0.36	0.45	0.47	0.24	0.64	0.49	1.00								
14 Publications with a sex or gender dimension MM	-0.31	-0.14	0.09	-0.08	0.02	0.08	0.35	0.25	0.26	0.05	-0.07	0.08	-0.03	1.00							
15 Segregation in the pipeline	0.85	0.82	0.65	0.59	0.42	0.21	0.19	0.21	0.19	0.00	0.56	0.46	0.65	-0.27	1.00						
16 Research careers and sectors	0.57	0.58	0.81	0.71	0.80	0.47	0.41	0.30	0.37	0.04	0.82	0.54	0.69	0.01	0.69	1.00					
17 Career progression	0.21	0.15	0.52	0.04	0.53	0.95	0.91	0.35	0.19	0.15	0.72	0.51	0.40	0.21	0.22	0.48	1.00				
18 Representation in decision-making positions	0.26	0.03	0.26	0.26	0.23	0.21	0.31	0.64	0.92	0.80	0.21	-0.02	0.49	0.24	0.18	0.32	0.27	1.00			
19 Research participation	0.53	0.61	0.81	0.47	0.64	0.55	0.55	0.41	0.35	0.11	0.84	0.70	0.93	-0.02	0.68	0.81	0.59	0.37	1.00		
20 Gender dimension in research and innovation content	-0.31	-0.14	0.09	-0.08	0.02	0.08	0.35	0.25	0.26	0.05	-0.07	0.08	-0.03	1.00	-0.27	0.01	0.21	0.24	-0.02	1.00	
21 Index	0.43	0.41	0.71	0.42	0.58	0.57	0.70	0.59	0.65	0.36	0.65	0.49	0.71	0.49	0.51	0.72	0.68	0.68	0.76	0.49	1.00

5.3 Summary

These iterations provide a solid basis for the *She Figures* Index measurement framework. It relies on a final set of 14 indicators, distributed within six dimensions relevant to gender equality in the context of research and innovation in Europe. The next section details the multi-modelling procedure applied to this set of indicators to determine the final model of aggregation and weighting to be used.

6 Multi-modelling results

To construct the *She Figures* Index, a multi-modelling approach has been considered, using the data from the latest *She Figures* report at the time of writing. The principle of multi-modelling is that when faced with uncertainty, computing all possible versions can guide the choice of the final methodology. This makes an Index not only more robust methodologically, but also often politically more acceptable. The results of this work on the development of the *She Figures* Index is informed by the methodological work conducted by the Joint Research Centre, and a methodological consultation meeting with COIN (Competence Centre on Composite Indicators and Scoreboards) took place on 7 July 2023 (for more information, see [About the Competence Centre on Composite Indicators and Scoreboards | Knowledge for policy \(europa.eu\)](#)). These results are presented in this section.

6.1 Different set of alternatives

The different alternatives considered explored the effects of weighting and aggregation methods, as well as the type of metric (un/capped and curvi/linear). Alternatives are only computed for the case where the MM method is used for the gender dimension, as the assessment of the correlation structure suggested it was the most appropriate indicator (see Section 5). The principle of increased penalisation is applied, which means that only aggregation methods at the level of indicators that provide as much or more penalisation can be applied (i.e. if the geometric mean is applied at the level of indicators, it is only possible to use the geometric or harmonic mean at the level of dimensions). The list of alternatives is provided in Table 29.

Table 29 Different alternatives considered in the multi-modelling approach

	Metric	Aggregation method at the level of indicators	Aggregation method at the level of dimensions	Weighting method
1	Linear and capped (LC)	Harmonic mean (HM)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3
2				W2
3				Equal weights
4		Geometric mean (GM)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3
5				W2
6				Equal weights
7			Geometric mean (GM)	W3
8				W2
9				Equal weights
10		Arithmetic mean (AM)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3
11				W2
12				Equal weights
13			Geometric mean (GM)	W3
14				W2
15				Equal weights
16			Arithmetic mean (AM)	W3
17				W2
18				Equal weights
19	Linear and uncapped (LU)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3	
20			W2	
21			Equal weights	
22		Geometric mean (GM)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3
23				W2
24				Equal weights
25			Geometric mean (GM)	W3
26				W2
27				Equal weights
28		Arithmetic mean (AM)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3
29				W2

30				Equal weights
31				W3
32			Geometric mean (GM)	W2
33				Equal weights
34				W3
35			Arithmetic mean (AM)	W2
36				Equal weights
37	Curvilinear and capped (CC)	Harmonic mean (HM)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3
38				W2
39				Equal weights
40		Geometric mean (GM)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3
41				W2
42				Equal weights
43			Geometric mean (GM)	W3
44				W2
45				Equal weights
46		Arithmetic mean (AM)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3
47				W2
48				Equal weights
49				Geometric mean (GM)
50			W2	
51	Equal weights			
52	Arithmetic mean (AM)		W3	
53			W2	
54		Equal weights		
55	Curvilinear and uncapped (CU)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3	
56			W2	
57			Equal weights	
58		Geometric mean (GM)	W3	
59			W2	
60			Equal weights	
61		Geometric mean (GM)	W3	

62				W2
63				Equal weights
64		Arithmetic mean (AM)	Harmonic mean (HM)	W3
65				W2
66				Equal weights
67				W3
68				W2
69				Equal weights
70			Geometric mean (GM)	W3
71				W2
72				Equal weights

6.2 Distribution of scores – 72 alternatives

The distribution of scores across the 27 Member States from the multi-modelling process are provided in Figure 4 for the linear capped metric, in Figure 5 for the linear uncapped metric, in Figure 6 for the curvilinear capped metric, and in Figure 7 for the curvilinear uncapped metric. As expected, by construction, the scores are lower overall for the linear metrics than the curvilinear metrics. However, capping or uncapping provides broadly similar distribution of scores.

What is apparent is that the use of the geometric and harmonic means pulls down some of the scores quite significantly, as a result of the presence of low values close to 0. The results show that using aggregation methods that do allow for less compensation (geometric and harmonic means) generates ‘penalties’ for some Member States that are large. This is not seen as desirable, as it is caused by the presence of ‘0’ (recoded as 0.01), with a disproportionate penalty for data points that tend to this value.

The distributions of scores and ranks by Member State are provided in Figure 8 and Figure 9 respectively. This confirms that the use of the geometric and harmonic means introduces a lot of variation in both scores and ranks, particularly in countries that perform less well in relation to gender equality in research and innovation. On the basis of the analysis, only the arithmetic mean as a model of aggregation was retained.

Figure 4 Distribution of scores by method – Linear capped

Note: AM – Arithmetic mean; GM – Geometric mean; HM – Harmonic mean; W1-3 – Weight options 1 to 3; LC – Linear capped.

Figure 5 Distribution of scores by method – Linear uncapped

Note: AM – Arithmetic mean; GM – Geometric mean; HM – Harmonic mean; W1-3 – Weight options 1 to 3; LU – Linear uncapped.

Figure 6 Distribution of scores by method – Curvilinear capped

Note: AM – Arithmetic mean; GM – Geometric mean; HM – Harmonic mean; W1-3 – Weight options 1 to 3; CC – Curvilinear capped.

Figure 7 Distribution of scores by method – Curvilinear uncapped

Note: AM – Arithmetic mean; GM – Geometric mean; HM – Harmonic mean; W1-3 – Weight options 1 to 3; CU – Curvilinear uncapped.

Figure 8 Distribution of scores by Member States – 72 alternatives

Figure 9 Distribution of ranks by Member States – 72 alternatives

6.3 Distribution of scores – 12 alternatives

The multi-model analysis was replicated with only the use of the arithmetic mean as a method of aggregation, yielding a narrower set of 12 alternatives. The associated distributions of scores and ranks by Member State are provided in Figure 10 Figure 8 and Figure 11 respectively. Using only the arithmetic mean as a method of aggregation decreases the variation in scores significantly, however, there is still substantial variation in ranks for some Member States.

Figure 10 Distribution of scores by Member States – 12 alternatives

Figure 11 Distribution of ranks by Member States – 12 alternatives

A closer examination of the Member States for which these large variations in ranks are occurring show the origin of the issue. In the case of Latvia, the scores are lowest when the set of weights W3 is used (Figure 12), corresponding to ranks ranging from 14 to 20, well below the median rank of 7.5 (Figure 13). A similar pattern emerges for Romania, as illustrated in

Figure 14 for scores and Figure 15 for ranks. In the case of Malta, however, the effects of using W3 weights is reverse, providing much higher scores and ranks (Figure 16 and Figure 17). What these results demonstrate is that the calculation of the *She Figures* Index is very sensitive to the indicator measuring the gender dimension in research and innovation content. The use of the expert weight W3 gives more emphasis of this aspect, amplifying the variation in some Member States (see also section 8 for further results on this aspect). Noting that this indicator relies on a different metric, and the variation observed in the multi-modelling analysis leads to the conclusion that it is more sensible to use a methodology for weighting that does not provide disproportionate weighting to this dimension, and hence instead using the option of equal weights (W1).

Figure 12 Example: Scores for Latvia across the 12 alternatives

Figure 13 Example: Ranks for Latvia across the 12 alternatives

Figure 14 Example: Scores for Romania across the 12 alternatives

Figure 15 Example: Ranks for Romania across the 12 alternatives

Figure 16 Example: Scores for Malta across the 12 alternatives

Figure 17 Example: Ranks for Malta across the 12 alternatives

6.4 Summary

The multi-modelling analysis examined the effects of aggregation methods on the scores and ranks of the *She Figures* Index, concluding that the use of aggregation methods that do not allow for full compensation unduly penalise Member States that perform less well, relative to other Member States. The option of using the arithmetic mean as a method of aggregation is thus seen as preferable. The multi-modelling analysis has also shown that the indicator measuring the gender dimension in research and innovation content not only relies on a different metric, but also introduces a lot of variability in the *She Figures* Index scores and ranks. For this reason, using expert weights (W2 and W3) that magnify this effect is not desirable, and equal weights (W1) are preferred instead.

7 Final model used to compute the She Figures Index

The in-depth analysis and assessment conducted in this methodological report have informed a final model for computing the *She Figures* Index. This section summarises the steps and provides scores and ranks for the dimensions and overall *She Figures* Index.

7.1 Overview of final methodological steps

These methodological choices can be summarised as using the following:

1. Curvilinear uncapped metric for shares (CU), providing a gender equality perspective and reflecting a greater emphasis on gender balance in research and innovation
2. Min-max metric for level of gender dimension in research and innovation content (MM), using the observed minimum and maximum as thresholds of the extent to which the gender dimension can be integrated
3. Arithmetic mean at the level of indicators and dimensions, allowing for compensation
4. Equal weights for aggregating indicators and dimensions.

An added benefit of using the arithmetic mean and equal weights is that they are easily interpretable and communicated.

7.2 Scores of the *She Figures* Index

The *She Figures* Index scores are calculated using indicators from the 2021 edition and the 2024 edition (Table 30 and Table 31). The list of indicators is provided respectively in Table 32. For ease of interpretation, all scores are rescaled so that they fall on the interval 0 to 100. For the 2021 edition, the *She Figures* Index ranges from scores of 55.9 to 87.5 (Figure 18), where 100 represents the gender equality point. By 2024, this range had narrowed slightly, from 60.1 to 87.6, with the top of the score distribution remaining unchanged (Figure 19).

Figure 18 Scores of the *She Figures* Index (2021 edition)

Figure 19 Scores of the She Figures Index (2024 edition)

Progress has been achieved by the majority of MS, particularly those with lower scores. The most progress was achieved in Slovakia and the Netherlands with increases of about 10 points or more (Figure 20).

Figure 20 Difference in She Figures Index scores between the 2021 and 2024 editions

Looking at the results across domains (Figure 21 and Figure 22) shows that scores are highest for the share of women and men as researchers in different sectors, as well as in grade A and B positions. The representation of women and men in decision-making positions has improved in a number of MS.

Figure 21 Distribution of scores across domains (2021 edition)

Figure 22 Distribution of scores across domains (2024 edition)

Table 30 Scores of the She Figures Index overall and across dimensions (2021 edition)

	Segregation in the pipeline	Research sectors	Career progression	Decision-making	Research participation	Gender dimension in research and innovation content	She Figures Index
SE	79.4	89.0	90.3	98.8	67.6	100.0	87.5
HR	78.2	97.0	98.9	71.9	80.5	91.6	86.4
LT	82.6	94.6	97.7	97.7	75.1	63.4	85.2
FI	77.6	85.2	92.3	87.3	70.2	77.0	81.6
BG	93.0	96.5	97.7	90.8	71.2	30.7	80.0
ES	83.4	94.4	85.7	80.6	76.5	49.5	78.4
DK	75.3	92.9	80.0	93.6	64.5	61.9	78.0
LV	91.1	98.4	99.4	95.6	79.4	0.8	77.4
PT	85.9	92.2	88.1	78.1	81.5	37.5	77.2
EE	79.6	90.0	96.9	48.1	76.0	62.5	75.5
SI	69.9	89.0	92.5	94.2	69.0	27.7	73.7
IE	81.9	91.1	85.4	82.7	64.5	36.0	73.6
PL	70.5	91.0	85.4	66.7	74.0	42.3	71.7
AT	71.1	83.8	77.6	89.0	52.3	34.5	68.0
EL	75.7	92.0	78.5	52.5	65.6	43.6	68.0
RO	97.0	97.3	98.3	38.4	75.0	0.0	67.7
BE	66.0	90.7	75.4	72.5	68.6	29.5	67.1
MT	25.9	78.1	99.2	58.9	49.3	88.4	66.6
HU	66.0	84.2	78.1	71.0	62.1	35.9	66.2
IT	82.2	88.1	83.5	59.3	64.7	15.4	65.5
NL	66.2	84.8	76.2	54.9	65.7	45.6	65.5
SK	58.3	84.3	88.1	45.9	62.5	38.4	62.9
CY	72.1	92.0	65.9	36.9	46.5	63.7	62.8
FR	82.8	85.4	89.2	44.9	65.6	6.5	62.4
LU	48.1	80.0	74.1	65.2	55.5	21.3	57.4
DE	57.6	79.3	71.9	60.2	55.2	14.3	56.4
CZ	53.4	76.8	81.7	37.5	56.5	29.3	55.9

Table 31 Scores of the She Figures Index overall and across dimensions (2024 edition)

	Segregation in the pipeline	Research sectors	Career progression	Decision-making	Research participation	Gender dimension in research and innovation content	She Figures Index
SE	80.5	91.7	92.7	91.7	68.9	100.0	87.6
LT	79.9	94.0	98.2	89.5	75.7	69.6	84.5
FI	75.9	86.1	93.4	91.5	67.1	71.0	80.8
HR	82.1	94.2	99.4	39.1	74.0	89.0	79.6
ES	74.5	94.4	85.5	82.4	71.5	65.7	79.0
IE	84.2	91.3	91.6	96.1	65.7	42.1	78.5
DK	77.1	91.6	83.1	93.5	68.3	55.3	78.1
BG	90.6	96.9	99.4	88.8	73.6	18.8	78.0
NL	78.1	90.6	85.1	98.0	66.0	41.2	76.5
PT	81.3	93.2	89.4	82.3	72.2	35.0	75.6
EE	80.0	87.5	97.7	77.9	69.5	39.9	75.4
RO	96.1	95.9	97.3	69.0	83.2	3.9	74.2
LV	82.5	95.3	99.7	99.0	66.9	0.0	73.9
IT	80.2	90.4	88.3	87.4	78.4	15.9	73.4
SK	72.5	84.9	96.8	86.1	64.8	33.0	73.0
PL	67.0	90.5	89.4	73.9	67.5	46.0	72.4
SI	50.1	91.0	95.1	91.7	71.1	30.8	71.7
EL	90.3	92.4	81.5	58.0	69.7	36.5	71.4
BE	59.4	90.2	80.4	96.8	68.9	23.9	69.9
AT	69.4	85.6	83.7	87.7	55.7	35.1	69.5
HU	71.1	83.9	78.8	66.7	60.5	42.2	67.2
CZ	65.6	78.9	96.6	66.7	56.0	27.2	65.2
FR	78.9	87.5	91.7	52.4	71.7	6.1	64.7
MT	42.8	88.0	95.8	56.3	59.0	34.9	62.8
DE	60.1	81.4	78.4	85.8	56.6	14.4	62.8
CY	67.6	93.0	66.3	38.0	50.3	61.1	62.7
LU	64.2	78.9	74.1	65.2	63.9	14.3	60.1

7.3 Summary

The scores of the She Figures Index show that no country has managed gender equality in R&I. While the range of scores has slightly narrowed, this is related to slightly higher scores among the countries with lower levels of gender equality, with the top score remaining unchanged.

8 Robustness checks

This section provides an overview of the quality checks performed on the She Figures Index, in line with the recommendations of the Joint Research Centre’s Competence Centre on Composite Indicators and Scoreboards (COIN).

8.1 Assessment of correlation structure

Assessments of the correlation structure for the 2021 and 2024 editions of the *She Figures* Index (Figure 23 and Figure 24) show that the structure of composite indicators is adequate. There are moderate to high positive correlations across indicators within the same dimensions; between indicators and their respective dimensions; between indicators and the overall Index score; across dimensions; and between dimensions scores and index scores. There are no strong negative correlations.

Figure 23 Assessment of correlation structure – 2021 edition

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1 Doctoral Graduates - ICT	1.00																				
2 Doctoral Graduates - Engineering manufacturing and construction	0.57	1.00																			
3 Researchers - Higher Education	0.69	0.65	1.00																		
4 Researchers - Government	0.62	0.64	0.60	1.00																	
5 Researchers - Business Enterprise	0.54	0.52	0.48	0.10	1.00																
6 Grade A	0.28	0.23	0.41	-0.11	0.42	1.00															
7 Grade B	0.28	0.33	0.40	0.00	0.44	0.73	1.00														
8 Heads of institutions	0.05	0.27	0.35	0.00	0.26	0.44	0.20	1.00													
9 Leaders	0.38	0.11	0.38	0.37	0.23	0.15	0.21	0.30	1.00												
10 Members and Leaders	0.24	-0.16	0.09	-0.08	0.04	0.04	0.10	0.14	0.50	1.00											
11 Authors	0.50	0.64	0.71	0.31	0.63	0.70	0.73	0.39	0.20	-0.01	1.00										
12 Patents	0.36	0.54	0.53	0.19	0.49	0.45	0.58	0.16	0.09	-0.27	0.59	1.00									
13 Beneficiaries of funding	0.60	0.52	0.72	0.56	0.37	0.37	0.33	0.32	0.50	0.14	0.54	0.48	1.00								
14 Publications with a sex or gender dimension MM	-0.24	-0.10	0.05	-0.20	0.09	0.12	0.26	0.28	0.21	-0.04	0.01	0.07	-0.08	1.00							
15 Segregation in the pipeline	0.94	0.81	0.76	0.70	0.59	0.29	0.34	0.15	0.31	0.10	0.61	0.48	0.64	-0.21	1.00						
16 Research sectors	0.74	0.72	0.73	0.50	0.91	0.36	0.41	0.26	0.37	0.02	0.71	0.53	0.59	0.01	0.82	1.00					
17 Career progression	0.30	0.28	0.43	-0.08	0.45	0.97	0.87	0.39	0.18	0.06	0.76	0.52	0.38	0.18	0.33	0.40	1.00				
18 Decision-making	0.34	0.13	0.41	0.23	0.26	0.27	0.24	0.60	0.91	0.64	0.27	0.05	0.49	0.23	0.29	0.34	0.28	1.00			
19 Research participation	0.60	0.67	0.78	0.46	0.56	0.56	0.60	0.34	0.35	-0.04	0.79	0.81	0.87	-0.01	0.69	0.72	0.61	0.35	1.00		
20 Gender dimension in research and innovation content	-0.24	-0.10	0.05	-0.20	0.09	0.12	0.26	0.28	0.21	-0.04	0.01	0.07	-0.08	1.00	-0.21	0.01	0.18	0.23	-0.01	1.00	
21 She Figures Index	0.51	0.47	0.69	0.30	0.59	0.55	0.62	0.56	0.67	0.26	0.63	0.48	0.61	0.55	0.55	0.67	0.61	0.72	0.68	0.55	1.00

Figure 24 Assessment of correlation structure – 2024 edition

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1 Doctoral Graduates - ICT	1.00																				
2 Doctoral Graduates - Engineering manufacturing and construction	0.05	1.00																			
3 Researchers - Higher Education	0.35	0.55	1.00																		
4 Researchers - Government	0.02	0.28	0.19	1.00																	
5 Researchers - Business Enterprise	0.27	0.64	0.50	0.15	1.00																
6 Grade A	0.12	0.38	0.37	0.23	0.16	1.00															
7 Grade B	0.07	0.55	0.40	0.20	0.26	0.70	1.00														
8 Heads of institutions	-0.14	0.28	0.52	0.28	0.22	0.38	0.28	1.00													
9 Leaders	0.24	-0.07	0.28	0.03	-0.17	0.12	0.03	0.26	1.00												
10 Members and Leaders	-0.07	-0.10	0.27	0.23	-0.03	-0.09	0.00	0.28	0.46	1.00											
11 Authors	0.21	0.72	0.71	0.39	0.65	0.64	0.73	0.40	0.12	0.04	1.00										
12 Patents	0.39	0.07	0.03	0.07	0.24	0.02	0.14	-0.33	-0.05	0.07	0.13	1.00									
13 Beneficiaries of funding	0.27	0.50	0.66	0.09	0.40	0.47	0.51	0.36	0.34	0.11	0.62	0.11	1.00								
14 Publications with a sex or gender dimension MM	0.01	0.12	0.24	0.26	0.14	-0.05	0.16	0.24	-0.20	-0.27	0.19	-0.27	0.12	1.00							
15 Segregation in the pipeline	0.93	0.41	0.52	0.12	0.48	0.25	0.26	-0.03	0.19	-0.10	0.45	0.39	0.43	0.05	1.00						
16 Research sectors	0.29	0.69	0.63	0.35	0.97	0.24	0.33	-0.10	0.06	0.75	0.22	0.46	0.21	0.52	1.00						
17 Career progression	0.11	0.46	0.40	0.23	0.20	0.98	0.84	0.38	0.10	-0.07	0.71	0.06	0.51	0.01	0.27	0.28	1.00				
18 Decision-making	0.06	0.05	0.48	0.20	-0.02	0.22	0.14	0.67	0.85	0.67	0.26	-0.16	0.40	-0.09	0.08	0.10	0.21	1.00			
19 Research participation	0.43	0.51	0.58	0.20	0.53	0.45	0.56	0.12	0.19	0.11	0.69	0.66	0.78	-0.03	0.58	0.59	0.51	0.20	1.00		
20 Gender dimension in research and innovation content	0.01	0.12	0.24	0.26	0.14	-0.05	0.16	0.24	-0.20	-0.27	0.19	-0.27	0.12	1.00	0.05	0.21	0.01	-0.09	-0.03	1.00	
21 She Figures Index	0.43	0.48	0.75	0.40	0.46	0.44	0.54	0.56	0.34	0.10	0.71	0.04	0.68	0.59	0.57	0.60	0.50	0.48	0.58	0.58	1.00

8.2 Assessment of robustness of the scores and ranks by dimension

A robustness check was performed to understand the contribution of each dimension (Figure 25). This is done by subsequently removing each dimension in the computation of the *She Figures* Index, and assess the impact in terms of scores and ranks. This assessment shows that there is relative homogeneity in scores and ranks when the first five dimensions are removed from the calculation. However, the effect is more pronounced in relation to the dimension on the gender dimension in research and innovation content, which has a stronger effect on final scores and ranks. This information shows that countries can make most progress by addressing gender equality in that area.

Figure 25 Assessment of robustness of the scores and ranks by dimension

	Without segregation in the pipeline	Without research sectors	Without career progression	Without decision-making	Without research participation	Without the gender dimension	She Figures Index	Without segregation in the pipeline	Without research sectors	Without career progression	Without decision-making	Without research participation	Without the gender dimension
SE	89.0	86.8	86.6	86.8	91.3	85.1	1	1	1	1	2	1	6
LT	85.4	82.6	81.7	83.5	86.2	87.5	2	2	2	2	3	2	4
FI	81.8	79.8	78.3	78.7	83.6	82.8	3	3	3	3	4	3	10
HR	79.1	76.7	75.7	87.7	80.7	77.7	4	5	4	7	1	5	18
ES	79.9	75.9	77.7	78.3	80.5	81.7	5	4	6	4	5	6	13
IE	77.4	75.9	75.9	75.0	81.1	85.8	6	7	5	6	9	4	5
DK	78.3	75.4	77.1	75.1	80.1	82.7	7	6	7	5	8	7	11
BG	75.5	74.2	73.7	75.9	78.9	89.9	8	10	8	9	6	8	1
NL	76.2	73.7	74.8	72.2	78.6	83.6	9	8	9	8	13	9	9
PT	74.4	72.0	72.8	74.2	76.2	83.7	10	12	11	10	11	11	8
EE	74.5	73.0	71.0	74.9	76.6	82.5	11	11	10	11	10	10	12
RO	69.9	69.9	69.6	75.3	72.4	88.3	12	18	14	13	7	15	3
LV	72.2	69.6	68.7	68.9	75.3	88.7	13	15	15	16	17	12	2
IT	72.1	70.0	70.4	70.6	72.4	84.9	14	16	13	12	15	16	7
SK	73.1	70.6	68.3	70.4	74.7	81.0	15	14	12	17	16	13	14
PL	73.5	68.8	69.0	72.1	73.4	77.7	16	13	16	15	14	14	19
SI	76.0	67.8	67.0	67.6	71.8	79.8	17	9	17	19	19	18	15
EL	67.6	67.2	69.4	74.1	71.7	78.4	18	20	18	14	12	19	17
BE	72.0	65.9	67.9	64.6	70.2	79.2	19	17	20	18	24	20	16
AT	69.6	66.3	66.7	65.9	72.3	76.4	20	19	19	20	22	17	21
HU	66.4	63.9	64.9	67.3	68.5	72.2	21	22	21	21	20	21	24
CZ	65.1	62.4	58.9	64.9	67.0	72.8	22	23	22	25	23	22	22
FR	61.9	60.2	59.3	67.2	63.3	76.4	23	25	23	24	21	26	20
MT	66.8	57.8	56.2	64.1	63.6	68.4	24	21	25	27	25	25	26
DE	63.3	59.0	59.7	58.2	64.0	72.4	25	24	24	23	27	24	23
CY	61.7	56.7	62.0	67.7	65.2	63.0	26	26	26	22	18	23	27
LU	59.3	56.3	57.3	59.1	59.3	69.3	27	27	27	26	26	27	25

8.3 Summary

The robustness checks done on the *She Figures* Index confirm that it is built upon solid methodological foundations, with a strong underlying correlation structure, and relatively homogeneous robustness in terms of both scores and ranks. As a result, this demonstrates that this composite measure provides a solid basis to capture gender equality in research and innovation in the EU.

9 Conclusion

This report has provided an overview of the development of the *She Figures* Index. By outlining the steps followed, and the rationale behind the decisions taken, it aims at providing a transparent account of the methodological steps underpinning the results it provides.

A composite indicator is necessarily a compromise between providing a synthetic measure and being as broad as possible. Going forward, as further indicators become available, its conceptual and measurement frameworks ought to be revisited, and where possible expanded. Further work could involve computing the *She Figures* for a longer time period, and where possible countries other than the EU Member States.

Table 32 She Figures Index indicators

Dimension	Indicator	Reference years ⁵	Imputations	Rationale
Segregation in the pipeline	Proportion (%) of women among doctoral graduates in Information and Communication Technologies	2016-18 and 2019-21 ⁶	Imputed using the average of bordering countries (DK: DE, SE for both time periods)	Scientific careers rely on a pipeline of graduates, and cannot be gender inclusive if there is not an equal representation of women and men.
	Proportion (%) of women among doctoral graduates in Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction	2016-18 and 2019-21 ⁷	None	
Research careers and sectors	Proportion (%) women researchers in the higher education sector	2018 and 2021	None	Women's and men's representation as researchers need to be equal in different sectors, such as in Higher Education, government or the private sector.
	Proportion (%) women researchers in the government sector	2018 and 2021	None	
	Proportion (%) women researchers in the business enterprise sector	2018 and 2021	None	
Career progression	Proportion (%) of women among academic staff in Grade A positions	2018 and 2021	Imputed using the average of bordering countries (CZ: AT, DE, PL, SK in 2018 and 2021; EE: FI, LV in 2018 and 2021); ES, LU: 2018 value used in 2021.	Women and men are not equally represented at different stages of their career, with an attrition of women among academic staff.

⁵ The reference year reflects the indicator values published in respective edition of the She Figures reports (2021 and 2024 editions). Exact reference years for country specific values can be obtained from these tables.

⁶ The number of doctoral graduates in certain subject areas can be very volatile, in particular for smaller countries, and therefore, the average of the past three years is taken. NL: 2017-18 only; MT: 2020-21 only.

⁷ The number of doctoral graduates in certain subject areas can be very volatile, in particular for smaller countries, and therefore, the average of the past three years is taken. NL: 2017-18 only.

	Proportion (%) of women among academic staff in Grade B positions	2018 and 2021	Imputed using the average of bordering countries (CZ: AT, DE, PL, SK in 2018 and 2021; EE: LV, FI in 2018 and 2021); LU: 2018 value used in 2021.	
Representation in decision-making positions	Proportion (%) of women among heads of institutions in the Higher Education Sector (HES)	2019 and 2022	CZ, LU: 2019 value used in 2022.	Women are under-represented as heads of institutions, limiting their strategic input, as well as member and leaders on the boards of academic institutions.
	Proportion (%) of women on boards, leaders	2019 and 2022	CY, CZ, FR, LU, MT: 2019 value used in 2022.	
	Proportion (%) of women on boards, members and leaders	2019 and 2022	CZ, LU, LV: 2019 value used in 2022.	
	Average proportion of women among authors on publications in all fields of R&D	2015-19 and 2018-22	None	
Research participation	Distribution of patent applications by sex composition of the inventors' team (%), ⁸	2015-18 and 2018-21	EL: 2015-18 value used for 2018-21	Women and men do not contribute equally to research content, as women are under-represented as authors or inventors, and are less likely to get their research funded.
	Number of applicants and beneficiaries of research funding, by sex	2019 and 2022	Imputed using the ratio beneficiaries to Higher Education researchers of bordering countries (CZ: AT, DE, PL, SK in 2019 and 2022; EL: BG in 2019 and 2022; FR: BE, DE, ES, IT, LU in 2019 and 2022; HR: HU, SI in 2019 and 2022; IE: UK in 2019 and 2022. LU: 2019 value used in 2022.	

⁸ This indicator is not available in the She Figures report, and is calculated using the share of a woman only, women only or women-dominated teams vs a man only or men only or men-dominated teams.

Gender dimension in Research and Innovation Content (GDRIC)	Percentage of a country's publications with a sex or gender dimension in their research content, by field of R&D	2010-2014 and 2015-2019	None.	The sex and gender dimension is insufficiently considered in research and the publications of findings
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